

EFFECT OF ECONOMIC FREEDOM ON RISKS OF VIETNAM'S BANKING SYSTEM

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Abstract

Economic freedom is an inevitable trend on a global scale, this has a certain impact on the operation of the banking system. The study was conducted to understand the effect of economic freedom on the risk of 22 Vietnamese commercial banks in the period 2010 to 2021. The study uses the fixed estimation method (FEM) and random estimation method (REM) and GLS for processing. Research results show that entrepreneurial freedom (a component of economic freedom) has a positive relationship with bank risk. Monetary freedom and financial freedom have not been shown to affect bank risk. The equity ratio and the ability to manage operating costs also have evidence to affect the risk of the banking system. Inflation also has an impact on bank risk. Then, the article proposes some governance implications for regulators.

Keywords: economic freedom, risk, financial freedom, commercial banking.

1. Introduction

Over the past three decades, economic freedom has been a very strong trend in countries (Shakhashiro et al., 2022). Economic freedom become an important trend in modern economics. It is practically expressed through various channels of expression (Yevdokimov et al., 2018). The world's economies are gradually integrating into the globalization trend to varying degrees. However, with events happening to the world economy, how an economy should liberalize is still a controversial question.

From a macro perspective, the impact of economic integration is often considered by researchers in the relationship between financial integration and economic growth. Several studies have provided evidence of the influence of financial liberalization on economic growth (Levine, 2018); (Edison, Levine, Ricci, & Sløk, 2002). This influence can be positive or negative (Edison, H. J., Levine, R., Ricci, L., & Sløk, 2002); (Ranciere, R., Tornell, A., & Westermann, 2006). Financial liberalization not only promotes economic growth through improved functioning of domestic financial markets, but also through stock market liquidity and the efficiency of financial intermediation by increasing competition from the penetration of foreign banks (Edison, H. J., Levine, R., Ricci, L., & Sløk, 2002). However, higher economic growth in developing countries is associated with higher financial volatility leading to a greater frequency of financial crises due to the easing of capital controls (Ranciere, R., Tornell, A., & Westermann, 2006).

In the banking industry, there is a lot of empirical evidence at the national and transnational levels assessing the relationship between financial liberalization, financial sensitivity, and linking financial liberalization with the possibility of increasing banking crises in the liberalized financial system (Shakhashiro et al., 2022); (Demirgüç-Kunt & Huizinga, 1999).

As a member of the World Trade Organization (WTO), the ASEAN Economic Community (AEC) and the Trans-Pacific Partnership (CPTPP), Vietnam's economy has made rapid progress, strong in the process of world economic integration. Accordingly, the banking system has also been constantly reformed to improve the efficiency of allocating and using financial resources. This also means that economic reform has been and will continue to be closely associated with financial liberalization in a mutually supportive relationship, opening up potential and development opportunities for the banking system. One of the results of the opening up of the economy or the entry of foreign banks is to create greater competition in the domestic banking sector that forces banks to take more risks to raise money, and being more efficient or productive may come with taking on more risk for the bank, although the latter may lead to a higher rate of the banking crisis.

2. Literature Review

Theory of financial restraint and liberalization

Keynes's theory of investment, saving, and growth states that, in a moment, high economic growth is always accompanied by inflation due to investment and not necessarily saving. Governments can actively influence growth rates by pursuing an inflationary fiscal policy that forces people to save to fill the gap between investments and saving. Besides, with the division of individuals into two groups, those with income over wages and those with income on profits, Keynesian theory suggests that a policy of high inflation and falling real interest rates will encourage individuals. Individuals belong to the income-over-profit group, so they have an incentive to save to increase investment and decrease consumption. On the contrary, the real income of the group with wage income will decrease, which encourages them to consume rather than save. The financial system at this time only plays a passive role in distributing capital to the economy. It only develops after the economy develops sustainably.

In contrast to the Keynesian theory, neo-liberalists argue that the financial system is the best allocator of financial resources through risk-sharing and time-bound transfers. In conditions of scarce investment capital, especially in poor countries, a liberalized financial system allocates resources most efficiently.

Economic freedom

Economic freedom is an economic term used in research and communication related to economic policy. Economic freedom refers to the ability of actors in society to carry out economic activities in a free market and free trade environment (Personal & Archive, 2015). The view of the free market and economic freedom holds that economic freedom is freedom in production, and trading activities as well as the freedom to consume any products, goods, and services without having to use them for improper interventions such as theft or force, or fraud.

To measure economic freedom, countries are currently using the Index of Economic Freedom developed by The Heritage Foundation in 1995 (Miller & Kim, 2015). This indicator includes 12 indicators, divided into 4 groups. First, the rule of law includes property rights, judicial validity, and government transparency; Second, government size includes factors such as tax

burden, government spending, and state budget health; Third, legal effect includes issues of freedom of business, freedom of labor and freedom of monetary policy; Fourth, the open market includes freedom of trade, freedom of investment and freedom of finance.

Business Freedom

Freedom of business represents the people's right to freedom of business. It is the ability to set up and run a business without undue interference from the state. One of the most basic indicators of economic freedom is the right to do business. On the other hand, business freedom includes the simplification of administrative procedures and the reduction of barriers that hinder the development of enterprises.

Financial freedom

Financial liberalization is the process of minimizing to removing state control over the operation of the national financial system, enabling the financial system to operate according to the rules of the market. The content of financial liberalization includes the liberalization of interest rates, the liberalization of commercial banks' business activities, the liberalization of foreign exchange operations, and the activities of financial institutions in the financial market. Thus, with financial liberalization, policies aimed at controlling interest rates and credit allocation are abolished. On the other hand, financial liberalization also aims to increase the level of competition in the financial market, which means eliminating legal inequalities between types of financial institutions in the market (Lewellen, 1970).

Monetary freedom

Monetary freedom as defined by The Heritage Foundation is the maintenance of price stability without any microeconomic intervention. In more detail, monetary freedom is an index built on two indicators, the index of inflation averaged over the previous three years and the ability to control prices. This index is a measure of monetary policy independence (Sufian & Shah Habibullah, 2014), as both inflation and price controls distort market activities. Citizens need a stable and reliable monetary (currency) system to serve as a reliable medium of exchange and store of value. This index is ranked from 0 to 100 according to The Heritage Foundation, the higher the index, the greater the monetary freedom.

International integration in the banking sector

Financial integration is the process of removing interest rate controls, privatizing state-owned financial institutions, loosening regulations on establishing new financial institutions, and encouraging financial institutions' expansion of scale, the scope of operations, and liberalization of international capital flows. Financial integration can be measured through the degree of financial liberalization in the banking sector and the openness of the domestic commercial banking system to the region and the world.

3. Research methodology

Based on reference to the research model of Ghosh (2016) on assessing the impact of economic freedom on banking risk in countries in the MENA region, the author proposes to apply a

research model for the case of economic freedom to bank risk for the case of Vietnam market as follows:

$$\text{LnZscore}_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 \ln(\text{Loans/TA})_{it} + \beta_2 \ln(\text{TA})_{it} + \beta_3 \ln(\text{NII/TA})_{it} + \beta_4 \ln(\text{NIE/TA})_{it} + \beta_5 \ln(\text{ETA})_{it} + \gamma_1 \ln(\text{GDP})_t + \gamma_2 \ln(\text{INF})_t + \delta_1 \text{BF}_t + \delta_2 \text{MF}_t + \delta_3 \text{FF}_t + \varepsilon_{it}$$

In which, Z_Score is used as a proxy for a type of risk of banks Meslier, Morgan, Samolyk, and Tarazi (2016). This index is calculated according to the following formula:

$$\text{Z_Score} = (\text{ROAA}_{i,t} + \text{ETA}_{i,t}) / \text{Sd_ROAA}_{i,t}$$

Where ROAA is the ratio of average profit and total assets, Sd_ROAA is the standard deviation of ROAA. To measure Sd (ROAA), the study uses the standard deviation of the rate of return and total assets for 3 consecutive years. A high value of Z_Score means that the bank's risk is low and vice versa. The variables in the research model are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of variables in the research model

Variables	Variable Symbols	Variable Description	Expectation	Data source
Dependent variable				
Bank risk				
Bank risk	Zscore	Estimates		Bank Scope Database
Independent variables				
Economic freedom				
Business Freedom	BF	This index deals with how easy it is to do a business, how easy it is to get a license, and how easy it is to close a business.	+/-	Heritage Foundation
Monetary freedom	MF	Prices and inflation are the two main factors that control the market. A policy of price stability without microeconomic intervention is an ideal environment for the free market	+/-	
Financial freedom	FF	The index refers to the loosening of government controls on banks, insurance companies, and capital markets. In other words, the index represents the separation of the financial system from the government system of a country	+/-	
Control variables in the model				
Internal factors (bank characteristics)				

Loan-to-total assets ratio	Loans/T A	The ratio of total loans is divided by the total assets of the bank.	+/-	Bank Scope Database
Bank size	TA	Size of total bank assets	+/-	
Diversification	NII/TA	Non-interest income/Total assets	+	
Operating costs	NIE/TA	Operating expenses are divided by total assets. This indicator refers to the bank's ability to manage costs.	-	
Equity ratio	ETA	Equity/total assets	+	
External factors (macro)				
Economic growth	GDP	Annual economic growth rate	+	IMF
Inflation	INF	Inflation of the economy every year	+	IMF

4. Data collection

Research data is collected from annual financial statements of Vietnamese commercial banks for the period 2010 - 2021. Banks have their mechanisms, especially banks with 100% state capital (Agribank); Vietnam social policy banks, Vietnam development banks, cooperative banks and banks with 100% foreign capital, joint venture banks, and banks with mergers and acquisitions activities will not be considered. Considered in this study. The data relating to the bank's variables are sourced from the Bank scope. The source of data on financial liberalization is based on the assessment results of The Heritage Foundation. Macro data is collected from the website of the international monetary fund (IMF).

To process data, the study uses quantitative research methods, fixed estimation methods, and random effects estimation methods, then the author uses the Hausman test to choose the appropriate estimation method for the model. In addition, the author also performs other tests such as variable variance, and autocorrelation, if one or more of these phenomena exist, the author will use other estimates such as GLS to overcome it to ensure high reliability of research results.

The first step is to perform a descriptive statistical analysis of the variables in the model to get an initial overview of the database. Next, analyze the correlation between the variables in the model to check for multicollinearity. Then, perform a regression analysis of the model based on the estimates in the panel data such as the fixed effects estimate (FEM), the random effects estimate (REM), and the regression model estimate generalization (GLS). Besides, the author also tests the phenomena that can cause unreliable results such as the phenomenon of variable variance, and the phenomenon of autocorrelation in the research model. The results after handling the above phenomena will be used by the author to analyze and discuss the research results.

5. Empirical analysis

Descriptive statistics are used to turn raw data sets into a more understandable form of aggregated information, describing the basic properties of measurement variables such as mean, maximum, minimum, mean, and standard deviation of the study sample.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics

Variables	Number of observation	Mean	Standard deviation	Min	Mean	Max
Z_score	184	12,29	12,60	1,20	8,48	98,72
Loans/TA	250	0,52	0,14	0,11	0,53	0,85
TA	250	17,57	1,46	11,88	17,59	20,81
NII/TA	223	0,02	0,04	-0,07	0,01	0,29
NIE/TA	234	0,02	0,01	0,003	0,02	0,03
ETA	247	0,12	0,08	0,04	0,10	0,46
GDP	262	0,06	0,01	0,05	0,06	0,07
INF	262	0,08	0,06	0,01	0,07	0,23
BF	262	61	1,31	58,30	61,15	63,80
MF	262	69,19	5,74	58,10	67,40	79,10
FF	262	31,6	3,68	30,00	30,00	40,00

Source: Vietnamese commercial banks

Statistical results show that the banks in the sample are concentrated in the group with a low Z_score, the economic freedom of Vietnam has not changed much, and the banks in the research sample mainly focus on business activities. Loans, income diversification is still low, expense ratio and total assets are concentrated in high-value groups, and banking activities are hidden with many risks.

The correlation between the variables in the model is shown through the correlation matrix. Through the correlation matrix, it is possible to identify pairs of variables with high correlation coefficients. If the pair of independent variables have a correlation coefficient exceeding 0.8, it is a sign that the regression model may have serious multicollinearity. Pairs of variables with the possibility of multicollinearity will not be included in the same model to avoid skewed reflection of research results. The variables in the research model have a distributive correlation from 0.0067 to 0.593. Thus, the model does not encounter severe multicollinearity (Wooldridge, 2003).

The results of the research model regression by different methods including FEM, REM, and GLS are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Research model regression results

Variables	LnZscore (FEM)		LnZscore (REM)		LnZscore (GLS)	
	Coefficient	P value	Coefficient	P value	Coefficient	P value
BF	-0,129**	0,032	-0,122**	0,028	-0,123**	0,027
MF	0,027**	0,037	0,022*	0,077	0,019	0,122
FF	-0,021	0,445	-0,020	0,369	-0,022	0,328
LNLoans_TA	-0,670	0,171	-0,510	0,096	-0,384	0,162
LNTA	1,481	0,716	0,492	0,758	0,409	0,761
LNNIITA	0,097	0,268	0,023	0,750	-0,014	0,841
LNNIETA	-0,720**	0,044	-0,509**	0,043	-0,422*	0,060
LNETA	0,620**	0,028	0,467**	0,046	0,385*	0,075
LNGDP	0,655	0,457	0,945	0,254	1,057	0,202
LNINF	-0,334***	0,002	-0,280***	0,002	-0,246***	0,006
Coefficient	4,006	0,732	8,028	0,192	8,990	0,112
F stat	1,84	0,0225	32,41	0,0003	30,10	0,0008
Number of observations	165		165		165.000	

Research results show that business freedom and financial freedom have a negative relationship with bank stability (Zscore), and variable BF and variable FF have a negative relationship with variable LNZ_Score. In other words, the increase in the business freedom index and the financial freedom index increases the bank's risk tolerance. However, based on the statistical results, only the impact of entrepreneurship on bank risk is statistically significant, statistically significant at the 5% level.

The impact of business freedom on the bank's risk tolerance is analyzed specifically as follows: BF has a negative impact on the Z_Score at a 5% significance level (95% confidence level), and the impact factor is -0.123. It shows that free business change by 1 unit will increase the instability in the operation of Vietnamese banks by 0.123%. The most common meaning of entrepreneurship is an environment without legal barriers and administrative procedures, a start-up company is easy to set up and easy to get a business license in and convenient way, moreover closing a business is not too difficult and time-consuming. In other words, free enterprise is a free, fair, and transparent market. The entry of competitors into a new economy is relatively easy. Business freedom opens up business opportunities that work for all areas including the banking industry. Therefore, as the business environment becomes more and more liberal, the banking industry will face some obstacles that increase its ability to accept more risks:

Firstly, competition to dominate the market and market share in the industry becomes more and more fierce, requiring banks to increase their risk tolerance. As argued by McKinnon

(1973) and Shaw (1973), representing a new school of economics, in favor of economic freedom, it proposes a government mechanism to loosen capital controls and remove barriers to economic growth. Importing can encourage foreign investment into the domestic economy and enable foreign banks and non-bank financial institutions to compete in the domestic financial market, thus increasing competition. Market. In the past, banks in Vietnam could be considered a monopoly in providing banking services (credit, payment services, etc.), and of course, obtaining a license to do business in this industry was an obstacle great for start-up companies. Currently, the banking business in Vietnam has been opened up a bit, although there are still many legal constraints, the object of the banking business is extended to domestic and foreign organizations. Since then, the pressure of the banking industry's competition in the context of Vietnam will increase, to keep the market and achieve the growth target, the bank can implement more reckless strategies, and increase the risk tolerance limit.

The index of monetary freedom and financial freedom has no evidence to affect the risk tolerance of banks. In other words, the control of market prices, as well as the involvement or reduction of the Government's deep intervention in the operation of the banking industry in Vietnam, has not been shown to improve or increase risks for banks. However, the negative correlation (although not yet statistically significant) between financial freedom (FF) and banking stability (Zscore) also sends out more attention-seeking signals for the control of financial institutions. Government in the banking system. The reason is that financial freedom means loosening the government's control over banking activities, which may contribute to reducing bank stability and increasing risks for banks. Banks with participatory government control often lead to designated loans, bypassing risk controls.

The ratio of expenses to total assets (NIE/TA) has a negative effect on the Z_Score at a 10% significance level. Regression results show that a 1% increase in NIE/TA will make Z_Score decrease by 0.422%. Thus, good cost management capacity will contribute to the stability of the bank's operations (lower Z_Score indicates higher profit volatility and vice versa). Poor cost management will erode profits, reducing ROA. In addition, the increase in profit volatility increases the bank's risk (decreased Z_Score).

The equity and total assets (E/TA) ratio has a positive effect on bank stability (Z_Score) with 90% confidence, a 1% increase in E/TA will make Z_Score increase by 0.385%. More specifically, the more capital participation of shareholders in the bank's capital structure will help the bank to be more stable. The empirical results of the study support the State Bank's regulation to force credit institutions to increase their charter capital, to improve and control risks in the Vietnamese banking system.

Loan ratio and total assets (Loans_TA) have a negative impact on bank stability but are not statistically significant. However, the results show that the larger the loan ratio, the higher the bank's risk. This implies that banks, because of the high credit growth target, easily lead to lowering risk assessment criteria. This result suggests that banks should consider extending credit freely, in addition to strengthening appraisal and re-evaluation activities carefully before large loans to control risk for the bank.

Bank size (total assets) has a positive impact on bank stability (Z_Score) but is not statistically significant. However, the results also show that the bank's asset size and bank risk have an inverse relationship, the larger the bank's total asset size, the better the risk. Larger banks have easier access to better-mobilized capital, in addition, the quality of customers will also be better because they can use capital at a lower cost. This helps the bank to be more selective about credit subjects, more compliant with risk control mechanisms, and thereby reduce risks for the bank.

Diversification is measured through the ratio of non-interest income to total assets (LNNII/TA). This variable has a negative effect on bank stability (Z_Score) but is not statistically significant. In other words, diversification increases the risk for the bank. The reason can be explained that the concentration of capital on other business tools (trading in securities, foreign currencies,) in addition to traditional activities (mobilizing and lending) easily leads to allocation. Inefficient resources, away from the main activities, increase the instability of the bank's income. Therefore, banks need to have more appropriate diversification policies, and diversify products and business activities, but limit the separation from the core activities of mobilization and lending. However, a positive view of diversification is that it can help banks better spread risks, penetrate deeper into the economy, and meet the maximum needs of customers.

GDP growth rate has no evidence of impact on bank stability (via Zscore). However, a positive relationship is found between GDP growth and Zscore. This shows that banks operating in a period of economic growth will contribute to increasing stability and minimizing risks. In the environment of GDP growth, it is easier for banks to mobilize capital and more convenient for lending, and businesses operate well, thereby fulfilling debt obligations with banks better. On the one hand, the bank increased the number of customers and increased profits and on the other hand, the accompanying provisions were also lower for the period of economic growth.

The inflation rate has a negative effect on the Z_Score, which is statistically significant with 99% confidence. Thus, inflation has had the effect of increasing bank risk. High inflation causes real interest rates to fall. In that context, depositors tend to withdraw their savings to increase investment. It is more difficult for banks to raise capital, so they are forced to increase deposit rates. At this time, the bank's input costs increase. On the other hand, due to high input costs, banks are forced to lend at higher interest rates and invest in high-risk investments in search of high returns to compensate. Such actions may have the effect of increasing credit risk for the bank, increasing bad debts, increasing provisioning costs, and making the bank's profits eroded. If that persists, it could reduce the bank's equity.

6. Conclusion and management implication

Firstly, bank administrators focus on reforming, increasing competitiveness, and having an appropriate risk management strategy in the trend of global integration and liberalization. As the analysis results of the thesis, the greater the business freedom, the more risks the bank faces. Business freedom is an inevitable trend of the market economy, in line with the policy of the State. Therefore, banks have no choice but to change and adapt to the new competitive environment, which is fair and equitable for the parties involved. Vietnamese banks have the

home-field advantage, available local customer sources, and especially an understanding of local culture, which are internal strengths that need to be maximized to help improve efficiency and effectiveness management. In addition, the bank considers moving towards a strategy to improve governance, improve competitiveness and learn changes according to the advancement of technology so that the bank can minimize risks in the process of entrepreneurship reform.

Second, banks can increase shareholder capital and manage costs well to reduce bank risks. Research results show that bank capital has a positive relationship with bank stability. This result further supports the State's request to increase the bank's charter capital. In short, in the trend of economic integration and freedom, to minimize risks, banks need to have an appropriate capital raising strategy and meet the requirements of the State. Greater capital participation also helps shareholders be more responsible for their capital, thereby being more careful with the bank's development strategies.

Third, law-enforcement and enforcement agencies need more solutions to contribute to improving business freedom and economic freedom in line with Vietnam's commitments to the integration process (WTO), AFTA, ASEAN, AEC,). In the strategy of the State, we always aim for economic integration in both breadth and depth. Therefore, to improve the growth of the domestic economy in general and Vietnam's banking system in particular, policy-making agencies need solutions to minimize procedures, simplify legal requirements, and avoid overlapping legal cross-border investment, especially foreign investment in Vietnam. State agencies create maximum conditions to attract new investment, and stimulate start-ups through solutions to promote and support newly established enterprises.

Fourth, the Government considers reducing interference in the operation of commercial banks. The research results show that the deeper involvement of the Government in the own activities of commercial banks will increase the bank's risk. Therefore, to reduce risks for the Vietnamese banking system in particular and the financial system in general, the Government should consider reducing the intervention and ownership in commercial banks. This is also consistent with the general policy of the State of equitizing State-owned enterprises and equitizing banks. The government can prioritize creating a "playground" that is safe, fair, and transparent enough for those involved in activities rather than interfering in them.

Fifth, State agencies including many ministries and branches need to help stabilize the economy and keep the inflation rate moderate to contribute to reducing risks to the banking system. Research results show that the higher the inflation, the greater the bank risk. Therefore, measures to develop the economy at an allowable level of inflation should be noted and maintained. In addition, banks also need to have their forecasting strategies, to control and manage the risks that may be encountered.

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